

➔ MONOREPOS FOR SCIENCE

~~FOR FUN AND PROFIT~~

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TL;DR

- ▶ Large, end-to-end RSE projects, like a science-gateway with a lot of moving parts, will eventually benefit from having independently deployable components.
- ▶ Separating them into independent packages is the answer but creates new problems.
- ▶ Keeping these packages within a single shared repository, a “monorepo”, gives us benefits of both.
- ▶ But with new challenges still.

Caveat

- ▶ I consider myself an expert at many things, in particular scientific software development.
- ▶ But I don't have any deep wisdom on monorepos!
- ▶ I only submit this as a conversation piece, to share my own journey and the challenges I'm working through at the moment.
- ▶ Join the conversation! :)

\$ whoami

Software

Systems

Geoffrey Lentner

- ▶ [@GeoffreyLentner](#)
- ▶ github.com/glentner
- ▶ rcac.purdue.edu/about/staff/glentner

Project Overview

LSST – we need better tools to deal with the scale of data coming ...

Supernovae: from 10^1 to 10^4 per night

Recommender Engine for Intelligent Transient Tracking

*“Crowdsourcing Earth
to Watch the Universe”*

End-to-End System

Swipe Right for Science!

Recommendation: *Keen Distracted Keller (ZTF23abgqzhi)*
Observing facility: *springboro*

ACCEPT REJECT

Facility: All Facilities
Current Limiting Magnitude: 18.5

GENERAL INFO MORE INFO

Coordinates (RA, DEC)
Sexagesimal: 00:31:54.02
-12:57:49.85
Decimal Degrees: 7.975, -12.964

Estimated Magnitude: 18.31

Filter: g-ztf

Culmination for springboro: 2023-10-14T00:50:00-04:00

Antares | Alerce | Lasair | MARS | Fink

Magnitude vs Modified Julian Date plot showing data points and a shaded prediction band.

FINDING CHART SCIENCE IMAGES

Finding chart showing a star field with a central target marked by a crosshair.

Monoliths – I choose you!

- ▶ Project contained within single installable package.
- ▶ Every target host has the entire solution installed even only for a limited use-case.
- ▶ App server, HPC cluster, end-user PC ...
- ▶ Admin tasks, workflows, pipeline, user-auth, server, web app, cli-client, etc.

Single Package

```
.
├── LICENSE
├── pyproject.toml
├── ...
├── src/
│   └── refitt/
│       └── ...
├── tests/
│   └── ...
```

All the things

```
.
├── LICENSE
├── pyproject.toml
├── ...
├── src/
│   ├── refitt/
│   │   ├── __init__.py
│   │   ├── core/
│   │   ├── apps/
│   │   ├── services/
│   │   ├── data/
│   │   ├── api/
│   │   └── web/
├── tests/
│   └── ...
```

Benefits

- ▶ Single source
- ▶ Shared version history – atomic commits
- ▶ Simplified integration testing and debugging
- ▶ Simplified CI/CD (automation)

Where things break down

- ▶ A small client ... with 5GB of dependencies?

As a Library

```
#!/usr/bin/env python3

from refitt import client

# Get new recommendations
response = client.get('/recommendation', limit=10, facility_id=1234)

# Accept/reject recommendations
client.put(f'/recommendation/{response[0]['id']}', accepted=True)
```

Where things break down

- ▶ A small client ... with 5GB of dependencies?

As a Command-Line App

```
→ refitt api get /recommendation limit=10 facility_id=1234
HTTP/1.1 200 OK
Server: gunicorn
Date: Mon, 16 Oct 2023 20:06:27 GMT
Content-Type: application/json
Content-Length: 299
{
  "Status": "Success",
  "Response": {
    "recommendation": [
      {
        "id": 22,
        "epoch_id": 3021,
        "tag_id": 6231,
        ...
      }
    ]
  }
}
```

Breaking up

- ▶ Identify the discrete components into separate installable packages.
- ▶ The API can depend on core-library packages
- ▶ The data-science components are isolated
- ▶ Virtual packages grouping components for specific installation targets

New Problems!

- ▶ Loss of shared history
- ▶ Many repos to update (version bump?)
- ▶ Coupled components require duplicate commits
- ▶ Developmental drift

A monorepo of packages

Benefits (again)

- ▶ Single source
- ▶ Shared version history – atomic commits
- ▶ Simplified integration testing and debugging
- ▶ Simplified refactoring
- ▶ Simplified CI/CD (automation)
- ▶ Unified versioning

New Problems (again)

- ▶ Branching / merging strategies
- ▶ Ownership of components
- ▶ Tools don't seem to understand the structure
- ▶ ???

Thanks for listening

- ▶ Find me at “glentner” most places.
- ▶ Come talk to me later!
- ▶ Questions?